

PRINCIPLE OF LEARNING AND TEACHING SPEAKING SKILLS**Quvondiqova Dildora**

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Annotation: Foreign language learning is done for a variety of purposes. Some people study it to become translators, and good writing and verbal communication skills are required. Some people learn a language in order to teach it, and teachers need to be knowledgeable in all facets of the language, including grammar, writing, listening, and speaking. However, the majority of ESL students study the language to communicate, comprehend speakers, and express their opinions. Speaking is the most crucial ability they should possess. Instead of truly applying what they've learned, people all too frequently spend their time studying grammar and memorizing lists of words.

Key words: English language, language skills, methods of speaking skills, communicative language teaching

In The globe has essentially become a global village in the present day, and English is the language of communication. The English language has become the most widely used language in the world and is widely spoken. Scientific research, education, commerce, the internet, travel and tourism, media and newspapers, software, medicine, engineering, information and technology, entertainment, banking, and other fields all use English extensively. English is the language that is most frequently used for online communication and commercial correspondence. Additionally, the majority of literature about higher education are written and published in English. Many people are learning the English language because of its many benefits in order to succeed in their endeavors. modern days, the whole world has become a global village and people communicate with each other in a common language, i.e., English. The English language is spoken all over the world and it has attained the status of the global language. English is the language widely

used in the field of scientific research, education, business, the internet, travel and tourism, media and newspapers, software, medicine, engineering, information and technology, entertainment, banking and so on. English is the language that is used mostly for business correspondence and internet purposes. Furthermore, most of the books related to higher education are published in English. Due to several advantages of English, many people are learning the English language to attain fruitful results in them.

The Basic Language Skills of English

The majority of people who strive to study a foreign language do so because English is used for worldwide communication. The four fundamental language skills—listening, speaking, reading, and writing—must be learned during this process. Speaking and writing, on the other hand, are active skills or productive abilities. Listening and reading are passive or receptive skills. Due to the fact that learners do not demonstrate their talent in using listening and reading, these skills are regarded as passive or receptive. They don't actually speak or write anything; they only read or listen to it. While learners must construct their own sentences, they need a lot of practice and must acquire a variety of grammar, vocabulary, and sentence-related concepts.

Communication plays a vital role in getting success in all fields. Language is used as a tool for communication. Moreover, people cannot achieve their aims, objectives, and goals without using proper language to communicate. Therefore, there is a need for a language to communicate with others those who live all around the globe. As English is considered the international language and it is spoken all over the world, it serves the purpose of communicating with the people who live in different regions, states, countries, and continents of the world. Speaking skill is the most important skill to acquire foreign or second language learning. Among the four key language skills, speaking is deemed to be the most important skill in learning a foreign or second language. Speaking is the skill that students will be evaluated on most in real-world circumstances, according to Brown and Yuke (1983). Despite its significance, teaching speaking skills has

received little attention, and the majority of teachers still teach speaking skills by having students memorize dialogues or practice drills. The current world requires that students have good communication skills, so English teachers must impart these qualities to their students in order for them to communicate more fluently and function better in everyday situations. To achieve our goals in this world, do we have to communicate our thoughts and ideas with individuals all over the world?

In order to compete in today's global market, every English language learner wishes to hone their speaking abilities. Furthermore, the majority of employment decisions are based on a person's communication abilities, particularly their speaking abilities. The examiners also notice the candidates' knack for speaking fluently and quickly. Job searchers who can demonstrate their skills at that specific time will hold the greatest positions in their careers. Additionally, these speaking abilities help professionals advance their careers. They can give brief talks in the classroom if they regularly exercise these abilities. Additionally, they develop self-confidence among one another and improve their ability to make decisions and solve problems. The students can effectively market their enterprises and form trustworthy commercial partnerships with other company partners.

The efficiency and problems of current methods of speaking skills.

The position of speaking in the hierarchy of language skills has evolved over the centuries. Rather ignored in the Grammar – Translation Method, it became a primary skill in the Direct Method. Audiolingualism brought even more focus on speaking, although the linguistic principle it was based on viewed oral discourse as imitative routine behavior in typical and predictable situations. The grammatical syllabus of the Cognitive Method incorporated activities in all language skills, attaching equal importance to each of them. Finally, Communicative Language Teaching added a more realistic dimension to teaching oral discourse by introducing numerous forms of interaction to the classroom and practicing the language in natural or probable situations which demanded defining of the discourse genre and the roles of participants. Although the contribution of CLT to developing forms of speaking practice in the language classroom can hardly be

overestimated, there is a growing tendency among researchers and practitioners to criticize it for its insufficient recognition of the complexity of speaking as a psycholinguistic process and of placing too strong an emphasis on information gap criterion as leading to artificial or impractical tasks. Speaking is currently regarded as the most fundamental talent to master, notwithstanding the inevitable criticism of the methods, approaches, or materials that are readily available. It has been seen as the ultimate objective of language learning ever since the communicative era began, and both teachers and students are now primarily concerned with its correct development. But it's also a widely known reality that mastering a foreign language in a classroom setting is not an easy undertaking. Even fluent language users frequently feel underprepared for speaking outside of the classroom after completing a course. When compared to the profusion of spontaneous speaking possibilities, the classroom presents fewer and less frequent opportunities for speaking, which makes it difficult for students to express themselves. In fact, selecting the most appropriate types of spoken discourse for classroom practice in a particular language course is a very hard decision which, unfortunately, hardly ever reflects the natural occurrence and distribution of communicative situations. Furthermore, an advanced language course should foster the growth of students' sociocultural knowledge—defined as "the culturally embedded rules of social behavior"—as well as their linguistic knowledge, which includes understanding of discourse and speech acts as well as the grammar, vocabulary, and phonology of the target language.

Conclusion: In order to acquire a second language, speaking instruction is crucial. A learner's achievement in school and later success in all aspects of life is influenced by their ability to communicate clearly and effectively in a second language. Language instructors must therefore give speaking lessons a lot of attention. Creating a vibrant setting where real discussion can occur is preferred to pushing kids toward rote memorization. In order to achieve this goal, a variety of speaking exercises, like those mentioned above, can greatly aid students in gaining the fundamental social skills needed in everyday life. Students get more engaged in

their education through these activities, which also increase their enjoyment and sense of purpose in what they are studying.

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